

A Dual-Process Cognitive Architecture for Tailored Behavior Change Interventions

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Abstract—This paper presents a cognitive-social robotic system for delivering personalized Behavior Change Interventions. Using the Transtheoretical Model and URICA questionnaire, the system assesses users’ readiness for change and ranks Behavior Change Techniques based on behavioral qualities. In a preliminary study, the system recommended stage-specific BCIs, demonstrating its potential to tailor interventions effectively.

Index Terms—Cognitive Social Robotics; Behavior Change; Transtheoretical Model; Opportunistic Reasoning

I. INTRODUCTION

Behavior Change Interventions (BCIs) are crucial for addressing public health challenges, from promoting healthy behaviors to managing chronic conditions. Traditionally delivered through face-to-face interactions or digital platforms, recent advances in robotics and artificial intelligence now offer new opportunities for more personalized, interactive, and engaging BCIs [1].

Cognitive social robotics is emerging as a promising approach to enhance BCIs by using robots to monitor behavior, adapt to users’ needs, and provide real-time feedback [2]. Through voice, gestures, and expressions, social robots create a more immersive and engaging experience, offering continuous support and adjusting interventions based on user progress, capabilities that static platforms like mobile apps struggle to match.

To develop an intelligent robotic platform capable of recommending effective Behavior Change Interventions (BCIs), the system needs to gather information about the user’s current state and have access to a comprehensive taxonomy of possible interventions, strategies, and techniques. Utilizing the Transtheoretical Model (TTM), which classifies individuals into stages of behavior change (Pre-contemplation, Contemplation, Preparation, Action, and Maintenance), the system can assess the user’s readiness to change. By monitoring this readiness through tools like the URICA questionnaire, and tracking key behavioral qualities, the robot can create a detailed profile of the psychological state of the user [3]. Furthermore, integrated reasoning systems allow the robot to process this data and

dynamically select the most appropriate BCIs, adapting interventions to the user’s specific stage in the TTM and their behavioral needs.

The objective of this work is to present a cognitive architecture for a social robot designed to assist patients with BCIs. Additionally, we introduce a first implementation of the system, where the intervention technique the robot should apply is selected by an opportunistic reasoner. This reasoner takes into account the user’s stage of change and a set of behavioral qualities to personalize the intervention and maximize the effectiveness of the robot’s actions.

II. PROPOSED COGNITIVE ARCHITECTURE

The proposed architecture is built upon the concept of dual-process theory, which divides cognitive operations into two distinct systems, i.e. System 1 and System 2, taking inspiration from Daniel Kahneman’s theory of human cognition [4]. In the context of BCIs, this dual-process framework ensures that the robotic system can manage both real-time interactions with the user and long-term strategic planning to guide the behavior change journey. Fig. 1 presents the block scheme of the proposed architecture.

Fig. 1. Block scheme of the proposed architecture

System 1 is composed of two key components:

- **Profiling Module:** It collects and updates the user’s behavioral profile in real-time, using both objective data (e.g., sensor readings) and subjective inputs (e.g., questionnaire responses). The module tracks three key behavioral qualities: Self-awareness (SA), Self-efficacy (SE), and Engagement (E). SA reflects the user’s understanding of their unhealthy behaviors, SE measures their confidence in maintaining healthy habits independently, and E tracks their commitment over time.

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- *Interaction Module*: This module manages the robot’s real-time interaction with the user. It ensures the delivery of feedback, motivation, and prompts based on the current context and user profile. By adapting its communication style and responses to the user’s immediate behavior, the robot creates a more engaging and responsive experience, enhancing the user’s likelihood of engaging with the BCIs.

System 2 encompasses more complex decision-making processes and is responsible for determining the best course of action based on the user’s current stage of change and overall behavioral profile:

- *Stage Detection*: This component uses the TTM, leveraging tools such as the URICA questionnaire to assess the user’s readiness for change. This module ensures that interventions are aligned with the user’s motivational state and needs by identifying the user’s current stage (pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, or maintenance).
- *Opportunistic Reasoning*: It performs opportunistic reasoning by analyzing the user’s current profile and identifying the best opportunities for BCIs. By continuously monitoring the user’s progression and adapting to real-time changes, opportunistic reasoning ensures that the interventions are delivered at the most appropriate moments, maximizing their impact. Additionally, it incorporates knowledge of various Behavior Change Techniques (BCTs) and ranks these techniques based on the user’s behavioral qualities, ensuring that the selected interventions are tailored to the individual’s specific needs and state of change [5].
- *Strategic Planner*: This module generates long-term, personalized intervention plans based on insights from stage detection and opportunistic reasoning leveraging automated planning techniques.

III. PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the preliminary evaluation, 38 participants (mean age 44.3 ± 14.5 , 17 M, 21 F) completed a questionnaire including the URICA tool to assess the readiness to change and behavioral qualities of the participants (SA, SE, and E). The results showed that 16 participants were in the precontemplation (PC) stage, 20 were in contemplation (C), and 2 were in preparation. Given the high occurrence in the early stages, 4 representative participants (P1-P4) were selected to test the system’s ability to recommend tailored BCTs. Fig. 2 reports the behavioral qualities reported by participants and the BCTs ranking provided by the proposed architecture.

The robot identified relevant techniques for each stage, with clusters such as ComparisonOfBehavior, NaturalConsequences, and SocialSupport recommended for PC, while Antecedents, SelfBelief, and ShapingKnowledge were selected for C stage. Some techniques were shared across stages, while others were stage-specific.

Fig. 2. Behaviour qualities and recommended BCTs per each representative participant.

The ranking of these techniques was also an important feature of the system. The robot dynamically ranked the BCTs based on each participant’s behavioral qualities. For participants in the PC stage, the system prioritized techniques that stimulate SA, as this is often the most critical area for improvement in the early stages. For example, a participant with a low SA score would be presented with interventions that strongly emphasize the need for awareness-building. Conversely, participants in the C stage had techniques ranked higher based on their capacity to enhance SE, ensuring that interventions aimed at boosting confidence and knowledge were delivered at the right time.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed cognitive-social robotic system demonstrates the potential to deliver personalized and adaptive BCIs by leveraging dual-process reasoning, the TTM, and behavioral qualities. Preliminary results showed the system’s ability to recommend stage-specific interventions, ensuring a tailored approach to each user’s needs. By ranking BCTs according to individual profiles, the system fosters more targeted and effective behavior change interventions.

Future research will explore the scalability of this approach and its application in real-world health contexts, particularly focusing on enhancing long-term engagement and adherence to BCIs.

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